

Bromide catalysed Oxidation of Fructose by Cerium(IV) in Aqueous Sulphuric Acid Solution – A Kinetic Study

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The rate of bromide catalysed oxidation of fructose by Ce^{IV} has been measured in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at constant ionic strength. The reaction is first order dependent each in fructose and Ce^{IV} . The rate of reaction decreases on increasing the concentration of hydrogen ion, and also decreases on increasing the concentration of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$. The bromide ion shows positive catalytic effect on the reaction rate. The value of activation energy has been calculated and a suitable mechanism conforming to the kinetic data is proposed.

Cerium(IV) salts have been widely used as an oxidising agent in sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acid media. This is due to its high oxidation potential in all the three acids as well as simple nature of its oxidising action involving only one electron transfer. In oxidation of oxalic acid by Ce^{IV} , Furman¹ and Willard and Young² observed that two moles of Ce^{IV} are required for one mole of oxalic acid. Recently, Sharma and Singh³ have also studied the oxidation of maltose and lactose by Ce^{IV} in sulphuric acid medium. They described that the rate-determining step is the decomposition of activated complex. The present study deals with the kinetics of bromide catalysed oxidation of fructose by Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulphuric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

In order to find out the dependence of the reaction on Ce^{IV} , the reactions were studied at different concentrations of ceric ammonium sulphate by isolation method. Under the conditions $[\text{Fructose}] \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, the order in Ce^{IV} was found to be unity. The values of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) are listed in Table 1. The variation of concentration of ceric ions had practically no effect on the rate constants, thus the order with respect to Ce^{IV} was unity.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF IONIC STRENGTH, Ce^{IV} AND FRUCTOSE ON REACTION RATE CONSTANT AT 40°

$[\text{Br}^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}, [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$				
$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{Fructose}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$	μ	$k_1 \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
2.00	12.50	1.68	2.02	
2.50	2.50	1.55	0.46	1.840
2.50	3.125	1.55	0.83	2.656
2.50	6.25	1.55	1.48	2.368
2.50	8.20	1.55	2.73	3.00
2.50	12.50	1.625	2.37	
2.50	12.50	1.700	1.96	
2.50	12.50	1.775	1.61	
2.50	12.50	1.85	1.37	
2.50	12.50	1.925	1.19	
3.00	12.50	1.68	2.13	
4.00	12.50	1.68	2.43	
5.00	12.50	1.68	2.57	

The order of reaction with respect to fructose was determined at different concentrations of fructose and at fixed concentrations of other reactants. The values of k_1 were determined and the results are presented in Table 1, which shows that the velocity constant is directly proportional to the concentration of fructose and the values of k_2 obtained on dividing k_1 values by concentrations of fructose are practically constant (Table 1) which shows first order dependence of the reaction on fructose.

Effect of ionic strength, bromide ions : The values of k_1 decrease on increasing the ionic

strength of the medium at constant $[H^+]$ (Table 1). Addition of potassium bromide shows positive catalytic effect of bromide ion on the reaction rate. The rate of reaction increases on increasing the concentration of $[Br^-]$ (Fig. 2A).

Fig 1 (A) Plot of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[H_2SO_4]$ at 40° , $[Fructose] = 2.50 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Br^-] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} M$; (B) Plot of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[H_2SO_4]$, $[Fructose] = 12.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 5.00 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 1.75$, other conditions are same as in (A); and (C) Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$.

Effect of bisulphate and sulphate ions : Sulphate being a better ligand can combine with Ce^{IV} to a varying degree forming various species. Several investigations⁴ revealed that in H_2SO_4 medium, ceric sulphate exists mainly as $Ce(SO_4)_2^{2+}$, $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ and $Ce(SO_4)_4^{4-}$ depending on the concentration of sulphate. From the study of the effect of $[HSO_4^-]$ or $[SO_4^{2-}]$ on the rate it was concluded that neutral $Ce(SO_4)_2$ is the reactive species. The inhibitory action of HSO_4^- (Fig. 1B) and SO_4^{2-} (Fig. 2B) is due to the conversion of reactive form of Ce^{IV} $Ce(SO_4)_2$ to the unreactive species $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ and $Ce(SO_4)_4^{4-}$.

The rate of reaction decreases on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid at varying ionic strength due to the conversion of reactive

species $Ce(SO_4)_2$ to the unreactive species $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$ (Fig. 1A).

Effect of temperature : The change in temperature seems to have markedly influenced the rate of reaction. The value of activation energy (ΔE) evaluated from the linear Arrhenius plot in the temperature range $35-50^\circ$ (Fig. 1C) in the bromide catalysed oxidation of fructose was found to be $106.09 \pm 0.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

The kinetic results (Table 1) suggest that the oxidation proceeds through an intermediate complex of fructose, Br^- and Ce^{4+} . The following mechanism is proposed on the basis of the results,

The rate law derived on the basis of above mechanism is

$$-\frac{d [Ce^{4+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [Ce^{4+}] [Fructose] [Br^-]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad (3)$$

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. A stock standard solution of sodium thio-sulphate was prepared⁵. Ceric ammonium sulphate solution prepared in 2N H_2SO_4 solution,

Fig. 2. (A) plot of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[KBr]$ at 40° , $[Fructose] = 3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 5.00 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 1.56$; (B) plot of $(-dc/dt)$ vs $[K_2SO_4]$ at 40° , $[KBr] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Fructose] = 12.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, $\mu = 2.225$.

was standardised iodometrically. The kinetics were followed by removing aliquot (5 ml) from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and the reaction was arrested by adding 5% KI aqueous solution (10 ml). The liberated iodine which is equivalent to the concentration of the unreacted cerium(IV) was titrated against standard solution of sodium thiosulphate.

Stoichiometry : In order to find out the stoichiometry of the reaction, the amount of Ce^{IV}

consumed was determined by titrimetry and substrate disappearance by measuring the volume of carbon dioxide formed, which was confirmed by lime water test. The stoichiometry thus determined was found to be 24 moles of Ce^{IV} to 1 mole of fructose. Thus, the overall stoichiometric equation could be written as

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